

THE IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING ONOMATOPEIC
WORDS IN JAPANESE LANGUAGE

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Abstract: In this scientific guide, in order to overcome the difficulties that arise in the process of learning Japanese, which is one of the mature examples of Eastern languages, we analyze the important aspects of imitation words, that is, onomatopoeic words, and also the Japanese language of such words. Important learning advantages are discovered.

This work is devoted to the study of onomatopoeic words that convey the sounds, using the example of Uzbek and Japanese languages. One of the most important conclusions that researchers who study sound symbolism and onomatopoeia come to is that "sound representation is not a special case in the structure of a language, a kind of isolated island, but a law that determines the origin, development and functioning of a language". The sounds that we pronounce carry a certain "symbolic potential", which allows them to convey both the phenomena of sounding and silent reality.

Keywords: Japanese language, Uzbek language, onomatopoeia, imitation, ideophone, sound reflexes, scientific research, alliteration, manga, emotional state, psycholinguistic, phone semantics.

Introduction

The object of the study is onomatopoeic vocabulary describing the sounds of animals and objects in Uzbek and Japanese; the subject of the research is the variability of expressing the same sound with the help of onomatopoeic vocabulary in the mentioned languages.

Sounds are divided into human and nature sounds. If human sounds appear based on the movement of the organs of speech, the sounds of nature usually appear based on objects: knocking each other, hitting, separating, separating, twisting, etc. Also, a number of sounds appear in our language based on imitating the sounds of animals: barking dogs, meowing cats, chirping birds, neighing horses, braying sheep, braying donkeys. Such words are called imitation words in linguistics. Imitation words are also words that express imitation of the state of animals and inanimate things. Accordingly, it is studied in two types:

subtleties of the language. So, *onomatopoeia* is a word that describes a sound that expresses movement and state, such as "tome-tome, tomo, shiro-shiro" in the Utebek language. - There are not two types of Japanese *onomatopoeia* as in Utebek, but several. Some Japanese *onimo* words don't actually imitate sounds, they describe feelings or actions. However, these words also have the same form and are similar to words that imitate sounds. That is, why we call them imitation words, or in other words, "onomatopoeia".

It is fact that a lot of scientific research has been conducted on imitation words. The works of such linguists as U. Tansman, A. Mikhlinen, SH. Kalliovalleye, A. Nannanen, A. Sebinen, Sh. Yanagawa, A. Jantohokera, Sh. Minayeva, E. Kytilayeva are an example of this.

When it comes to Japanese linguistics, in this regard, Japanese scholars also use imitation words, the scientists have also conducted a lot of scientific work on the issues of *onomatopoeia*. For example, as an example of this research, let's take the Hyogo-shi Japanese short novel "Kankoku Monogatari" published in 2008 by Yukino Kai, an accomplished linguist-philologist researcher. The sentences used in this novel are naturally used in everyday life by native Japanese speakers, providing natural words to analyze the meaning and usage of *onomatopoeia*. Such a short but short novel by Kankoku Monogatari reveals many *onomatopoeia* cases for the analysis of alliteration. The novel contains a total of 1222 *onomatopoeia* words. Analyzing and comparing the usage and meaning of *onomatopoeia* in everyday life with the *onomatopoeia* expressions mentioned in the novel Kankoku Monogatari will make language learning easier.

In statistics, there are relatively more *onomatopoeia* words in Japanese than in other languages. That is, why the Japanese use *onomatopoeia* at least once a day. They use imitation words, *onomatopoeia* to express even the smallest nuances. So, if you want to have a deeper conversation in Japanese, you should definitely learn *onomatopoeia* words.

In Japanese *Onomatopoeia*, a single word can have multiple meanings and uses, depending on the context of that particular sentence or paragraph. This means that the more meanings a single *onomatopoeia* has, the more it will be used, leading to different uses based on the context of the sentence, present. Considering the above points, we believe that it may take you more than a few years to truly master the Japanese language. Also, one of the best and fastest ways to learn *onomatopoeia* is probably by reading lots of manga! When you read manga, words like these are actually more common and help make the manga read more attractively and come alive. I believe that in the next stages of *onomatopoeia* research, more research is needed to understand the difference between voiced and unvoiced consonants in *onomatopoeia* that affect their meaning and usage.

Conducting a psycholinguistic experiment aimed at describing the *onomatopoeia* used by speakers of various languages and language learners as a foreign language should allow us to identify the universal and linguistic-specific in the use of *onomatopoeia*, as well as contribute to the description of how the lexical system of a foreign language is assimilated. Identification of linguistic universals and problems of learning a foreign language are questions that have been of interest to linguists for a long time and, despite a significant amount of

Conclusion

Onomatopoeia has a wide scope. Onomatopoeic words can be used both in speech and in writing. In writing, they can be included in "artistic, journalistic text and even used in advertising text. The purpose of the study of onomatopoeic units is the "interpretation of phonosemantic regularities" by the sound of the word and its *с. 89* , i.e. revealing the relationship between thoughts. In this case, the study of onomatopoeic words is primarily carried out with the help of an experiment that allows you to identify the meaning that speakers of different languages put into the word. Such studies make it possible to establish connections between the sound and meaning of words that exist among native speakers at the moment. Moreover, an important factor is also the correct choice of matching onomatopoeia. However, not every word can have a lexical match, especially if the onomatopoeia used to convey the sounds of one animal or object differ in meaning. For example, in the Koryak language, the sound of a cow is conveyed differently depending on the gender of the animal. There is no such distinction in Uralic language. Therefore, when comparing onomatopoeic vocabulary, it is important to take into account the "linguocultural and cognitive aspects".

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